

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF ZIRCONIUM. PART I. BENZILIC ACID

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Pure zirconyl chloride was obtained from zircon by a combination of the procedures given by Rossiter and Sanders and Hillebrand and Lundell. It is shown that benzilic acid precipitates zirconium from solutions up to 0.225*N* in HCl. Separation from most divalent and trivalent elements occurs in a single precipitation with the reagent in 0.20*N* HCl. In other cases (except tin and titanium) a second precipitation yields a pure zirconium compound. The precipitate of zirconium benzilate has the approximate composition, $O = Zr \begin{matrix} \text{OH} \\ \text{B} \end{matrix}, 4H_2O$ and is a basic salt.

Oesper and Klingenberg (*Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 1509) in a study of the use of glycollic acid derivatives in the determination of zirconium totally rejected benzilic acid on account of its "insolubility in water". Further, their results with the soluble sodium salt point to incomplete precipitation. However, the large weighting effect that the acid exhibits is a great advantage, especially in the determination of small quantities of the metal. On this account a more detailed investigation appeared very desirable. Although its solubility in cold is low, benzilic acid dissolves to an appreciable extent in hot water and the hot solution holds enough acid to precipitate zirconium completely. Further, under suitable conditions the zirconium benzilate precipitate is curdy and filters quickly through Whatman No. 41 filter. Thus, it offers a distinct advantage over many other reagents for zirconium.

EXPERIMENTAL

On the addition of a hot solution of benzilic acid to zirconium chloride or nitrate, there results first a turbidity; a few minutes' boiling produces a fine crystalline precipitate, which further boiling transforms into a curdy mass, not unlike silver chloride in appearance. This settles rapidly and washes quickly.

Zirconium Oxychloride.—Selected zircon (Travancore, 50 g.) was decomposed by fusion with 50 g. of sodium hydroxide (Rossiter and Sanders; cf. Mellor, "Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. VII, Longmans Green & Co., Ltd., London, 1927, p. 103). The fused mass was poured into 1.5 litres of water and filtered. The residue of sodium zirconate was dissolved in the minimum quantity of hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The dry residue was extracted with hot water and filtered. Titanium was removed by precipitating with diammonium hydrogen phosphate in sulphuric acid solution in the presence of hydrogen peroxide (Hillebrand and Lundell, "Applied Inorganic Analysis", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1929, p. 446). The phosphate precipitate was washed by decantation several times with hydrogen peroxide, acidified with sulphuric acid. The titanium-free phosphate was ignited and fused with fusion mixture. The cooled melt was extracted

with water and washed free of phosphate with 10% sodium carbonate solution. The residue was again ignited and fused with sodium pyrosulphate. The melt was dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid and filtered from any undecomposed residue. Zirconium hydroxide was precipitated from the filtrate with ammonia, filtered and washed with hot 2% ammonium nitrate solution. The hydroxide was ignited and fusion with carbonate and pyrosulphate was repeated to remove the last traces of phosphate. The hydroxide was next precipitated, dissolved in hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness. The residue was powdered, and shaken up several times with ether to remove any iron remaining. The residue was again dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid, and concentrated to crystallisation of the oxychloride. A second crystallisation yielded a product completely free from titanium and iron. A stock solution was prepared by dissolving about 30 g. of oxychloride in approximately 2.5 litres of 0.10 *N*-HCl.

Standardisation.—The ZrO_2 content of the solution was determined by precipitation with (1) mandelic acid (Kumins, *Anal. Chem.*, 1947, 19, 376) and (2) tannic acid (Schoeller, *Analyst*, 1944, 69, 259); 20 ml. of the solution gave $ZrO_2 = 0.0865$ g. and 0.0867 g. respectively. Mean 20 ml. = 0.0866 g.

Benzilic acid was prepared from benzoin according to the procedure given by Ballard and Dehn (Gilman, "Organic Synthesis", Collective Vol. I, John Wiley & Sons, N. Y., 1932, p. 82) and purified by two crystallisations from a boiling solution. The final product gave m. p. 149-50°. Other reagents were of the B. D. H. Analar quality.

Procedure.—The zirconium solution (ZrO_2 content about 0.075 g.) was acidified with the requisite volume of 2 *N*-HCl to give a final acidity of 0.2 *N* in 200 ml. and the mixture diluted to 100 ml. This was then boiled and to the boiling solution was added in a slow stream and with constant stirring a boiling solution of 1% benzilic acid (100 ml.). Boiling was continued for 10 minutes with stirring, at the end of which the zirconium precipitate collected as a curdy mass at the bottom leaving a clear supernatant liquid. It was then set aside for about 20 minutes, filtered through a 11 cm. Whatman No. 41 filter, washed with hot 0.2% solution of the reagent in 0.2*N*-HCl, ignited and weighed as ZrO_2 . Table I gives the results obtained.

TABLE I

No.	ZrO_2 taken.	ZrO_2 obtained.	Diff.	Remarks.
1	0.0866 g.	0.0866 g.	—	
2	0.0649	0.0648	-0.1 mg.	
3	0.0433	0.0434	+0.1	
4	0.0216	0.0214	-0.2	
5	0.0108	0.0108	—	
6	0.0021	0.0021	—	Vol. of the soln. 25 ml. and of the reagent 25 ml.
7	0.0011	0.0010	0.1	
8	0.0005	0.0005	—*	

* Vol. of the soln. 10 ml. and of the reagent 15 ml.

By suitably adjusting the total volume of the solution and the amount of the reagent it is thus possible to estimate as little as 0.5 mg. of ZrO_2 correctly. Again, the precipitate produced is so voluminous that smaller quantities, about 0.05 mg., can be easily detected.

Separation from other Elements

Besides zirconium, a number of associated and common elements, *i. e.*, thorium, titanium^{IV}, tin^{IV}, iron^{III}, uranium, manganese, cerite earths, aluminium, cobalt, zinc, copper and cadmium give similar precipitates with the reagent in neutral solution. However, in the presence of acid (HCl, 0.1N and above) most of these elements do not precipitate. Separation from these elements may therefore be accomplished by suitably controlling the acid concentration in the solution. For this purpose, the solubility of zirconium benzilate in hydrochloric acid was investigated by estimating the amount of zirconium precipitated from solutions of different acid concentrations. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

ZrO ₂ taken = 0.0433 g.							
No.	Overall conc. of HCl.	ZrO ₂ weighed.	Diff.	No.	Overall conc. of HCl.	ZrO ₂ weighed.	Diff.
1	0.05 N	0.0433 g.	—	5	0.20 N	0.0432 g.	-0.1 mg.
2	0.10	0.0432	-0.1 mg.	6	0.20	0.0434	+0.1
3	0.15	0.0433	—	7	0.225	0.0431	-0.2
4	0.175	0.0434	+0.1	8	0.25	0.0429	-0.4
				9	0.30	0.0406	-2.7

The precipitation of zirconium is incomplete in solutions of 0.225 N in HCl and above; and a suitable acid concentration for separation from other elements is 0.20N. Impurities were added in the form of nitrates or chlorides but their quantities have been calculated to the oxides.

In a few cases, thorium etc., a second precipitation was resorted to. For this purpose, the first precipitate was dissolved in a measured volume of hot 1:1 HCl, 4N ammonia was added to neutralise the excess acid and precipitation was repeated as previously described. Table III shows the results obtained.

TABLE III

ZrO₂ taken = 0.0433 g. Overall concentration of HCl = 0.20 N.

No.	Impurity added.	Amount.	Wt. of ZrO ₂ obtained.	Diff.	No.	Impurity added.	Amount.	Wt. of ZrO ₂ obtained.	Diff.
1	BeO	0.2165 g.	0.0433 g.	—	12	Al ₂ O ₃	0.4210 g.	0.0431 g.	-0.2 mg.
2	MnO	0.1894	0.0432	-0.1 mg.	13	Fe ₂ O ₃	0.1088	0.0435	+0.2 **
3	ZnO	0.2431	0.0431	-0.2	14	"	"	0.0432 a.	-0.1
4	NiO	0.2055	0.0433	—	15	"	"	0.0433 b.	—
5	CoO	0.1790	0.0433	—	16	Cr ₂ O ₃	0.1086	0.0436	+0.3 **
6	CuO	0.1860	0.0433	—	17	"	"	0.0433 a.	—
7	CaO	0.2548	0.0435	+0.2	18	ThO ₂	0.0686	0.0442	+0.9
8	SrO	0.1799	0.0431	-0.2	19	"	"	0.0433 a.	—
9	BaO	0.2050	0.0433	—	20	V ₂ O ₄	0.1055	0.0436	+0.3 **
10	U ₃ O ₈	0.1022	0.0431	-0.2	21	"	"	0.0432 a.	-0.1
11	*R ₂ O ₃	0.4360	0.0433	—					

* Cerite earths from monazite (exact composition not determined)

** ZrO₂ residue is slightly coloured

a. Double precipitation

b. Single precipitation but in the presence of 4 g. of ammonium thiocyanate.

Observations on the Separations

1. The divalent elements together with aluminium, the cerite earths and uranium are removed in one precipitation.
2. While chromium and vanadium do not ordinarily give a precipitate with the reagent in neutral solutions, small amounts accompany zirconium even in 0.2 N HCl. A second precipitation, however, removes them completely.
3. Iron and thorium do not precipitate individually in acid solution but accompany zirconium in small quantities which may be completely removed by a second precipitation. In the presence of excess ammonium sulphocyanide iron is held in solution and pure ZrO_2 , free from traces of iron results even in the first precipitation.
4. Tin and titanium are precipitated along with zirconium under all conditions and their removal is not possible with this reagent.

Composition of Zirconium Benzilate

The precipitate was finally washed with hot water and dried in an air-oven at 110° for several hours, *i.e.*, until its weight was constant. Weighed quantities of the dried precipitate were ignited to the oxide and the composition of the precipitate was surmised from the benzilate: oxide ratio in two different samples. The general composition corresponds to the formula $O = Zr \left\langle \begin{matrix} OH \\ B \end{matrix} \right\rangle, 4H_2O$; where B represents the benzoic acid radical. It is thus a basic salt with a slightly varying composition and direct weighing of the precipitate is ruled out.

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